

STATEMENT OF RESEARCH

Berat Özkan

G181804066

Title: Maintaining The Rule of Law: A Need for Increased Scrutiny

Introduction: After the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, the American Bar Association established an initial program to help several countries that were once a part of the USSR, such as Poland and the Baltic States, reform their judicial systems and promote the rule of law in a turbulent Eastern Europe. Communism brought in more conservative societies, leading to violations of human rights and political polarization. At that time, the only way to dismantle the heritage of previous totalitarian regimes was to draft legislation that codified the fundamental values of the rule of law, like equality of individuals and avoidance of arbitrariness.

The rule of law has been referred to as a core principle of democracy that holds all people, including civil servants and appointed officials, accountable for their actions. Fostering equity and fairness in modern democratic states, the rule of law warrants that government is restricted through authorities and politicians are sanctioned for misconduct, which is the necessity of preventing corruption—the distortion of the aforementioned principles. In order to understand the significance of the rule of law in creating healthy populations, the contextual elements of it should be explicitly expressed in the written law.

Core principles associated with the rule of law can vary among nations since they share different legal cultures. One such principle is judicial independence, which means judges must be protected from outside pressure and make decisions based solely on written laws. Academic literature has thoroughly discussed whether the rule of law is sufficient to protect fundamental rights, and one of the most crucial takeaways from research papers was that any democratic state that doesn't safeguard it can't promote good governance in civil society.

Declining commitment to the rule of law has been a thorny issue for modern democratic states, as it's a threat to their legal culture, which consists of several values and norms, including human dignity, equality, and freedom of expression. Also, there are some persistent challenges to the rule of law, with one being judicial misconduct that erodes public confidence in the integrity of the judiciary.

Observers have long recognized that judges are susceptible to outside pressures that could sway their decisions, and to protect judicial independence, they must feel free to determine the outcome of a lawsuit based solely on legal principles. Even though judges' authority is legitimated by law, judicial independence would be terminated if they decided on their personal bias.

Multiple studies have revealed that judges' life experiences and personal interests can impact their decision-making, and this alarming issue has raised questions about governmental institutions whose foremost aim is to ensure the independence of the judiciary.

Comprehensive reforms in the appointment process must be implemented to prevent partisan appointees from blocking non-ideological, law-abiding candidates. One thing to note is that some appointees unfairly cater to the ideological views of judges, endangering their impartiality and dignity. A portion of judges not only refuse to acknowledge their involvement in a case; they also see it as a conflict of interest. Judicial appointments in the United States have long been debated, with some political functionaries voicing their concern over the increased number of judges.

This research proposal represents student work and may contain errors.

Definitions:

- **The rule of law**: A set of ideals that suggest the government and its people are bound by rules.
- **Misconduct**: All types of inappropriate, unprofessional behavior.
- **Arbitrariness**: The state of being tyrannical, not constrained by authority.
- **Judicial independence**: The principle that suggests judges must function independently from any external pressure.
- **Personal bias**: The inclination to act in a way based on conscious or unconscious beliefs.

Keywords: judicial independence, government, corruption, personal bias, the rule of law.

Disciplines:

- **Law**: Administrative Law, Constitutional Law
- **Political Science**: American Politics
- **Sociology**: Political Sociology

The aims of this research are to:

- Define a set of principles the rule of law encompasses.
- Explain why principles of the rule of law are essential for national peace.
- Understand how judicial misconduct poses a threat to the integrity of the rule of law.

Research Plan

I plan to identify and review various cases in which judges failed to mitigate the impact of their personal biases on their decisions. Also, I will generate alternative solutions to handle common complaints of judicial misconduct.